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THE NECESSITY OF CHANGE IN ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE IN NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS

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ABSTRACT

As a result of the economic and social developments that have been experienced, the importance of organizations in the life of society has increased. With the increase in population and change of needs, people have come to a point where they cannot fulfil their own needs. This situation has brought organizations to the fore. Organizations are established to supply the needs of people and to achieve certain goals. Therefore, organizations are the basic elements of social life due to their roles. Non-governmental organizations have emerged with the organization of people in need to support against strong state and organizations. In this study, the development of non-governmental organizations, which are important elements of social life today, and their roles in society are examined. Globalization, developments in information and communication technologies have affected the society as well as the non-governmental organizations. Recent developments show that people will need much more support to the non-governmental organizations in the future. Non-governmental organizations need to adapt to changes in order to meet these people's expectations.

Keywords: NGO, Organization, Structure, Change

JEL Codes: M11, L10

1. INTRODUCTION

Scientific, technological and economic developments have had an impact on societies. These developments have caused changing in societies. Social change has also affected all the values that a society has. In this context, non-governmental organizations, which are important actors of social life, have to keep up with this change.

Non-governmental organizations have emerged as a result of the need for a different organization that will support individuals against power centers in the regulation of social life

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and the maintenance of relations depending on the rules. The emergence of non-governmental organizations is based on the development of the concept of civil society.

From the beginning of the industrial revolution to this time, great progress has been made in the field of information and technology. These developments coincide with a very short period of time in human history, but they are enormous in terms of their impact. This great change has deeply affected people and social life.

While the development of social life, the increase in welfare and in educational opportunities provide people to important advantages, they have also started to limit people's lives. With the industry, people have begun to become more and more lonesome therefore. It has left people unable to defend their rights in the face of the growing strength of organizations.

The ongoing pandemic, global warming and ever-increasing political uncertainties increase the need for non-governmental organizations. People need non-governmental organizations more in order to fight the pressure of global businesses, global capital and states. This situation requires non-governmental organizations to be strongly present in the field.

Since it is thought that these changes will continue to affect people and societies today and in the future, the problem of how non-governmental organizations should follow in the face of the negative consequences of these changes have been examined in this study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. The Concept of Civil Society and its Development

The basis of NGO's is the concept of civil society. History of civil society was well until the ancient Greek Times. Aristotle mentioned the concept of civil society as 'koinonia politike' in his "politics". The concept of civil society is referred as "societas civilis" in Latin (Doğan, 2015: 27-38). Civil society includes public as a whole.

In the classical period, the concept of civil society has been used synonymously with good society and seen indistinguishable from the state (Abubakar, 2021: 37). Another phenomenon of civilian society is the Roman "societas civilis" which was put forward by Cicero. The political discourse in the classical period was about to guarantee peace and order among the people who attached importance to the idea of a "good society". The second phase of civil society was the Middle Ages, which was the time when the social-economic thought of feudalism emerged. It was clear that there was absolutely no distinction between civil society and state in this period. In this period, clergy and churches shaped civil society. The Age of Enlightenment was an evolution for civil society reaching its present meaning. The formation of the modern capitalist state after the Enlightenment has been the stage of separating civil society from the state. In this process, the concept of civil society in the 18th Century turned religion against religion, placed to separate the authorities from the civilian population. We can consider it as the starting point of the emergence of society (Gündüz, 2015). Hegel completely changed the meaning of civil society and, unlike modern nation-state institutions, this led to a

modern liberal understanding as a non-political form of society. Hegel has also been the first political philosopher to emphasize it as a non-state field. Another thinker of civil society is Karl Marx. He criticized the Hegel's Philosophy of Law and believed that state-society dichotomy is directly dependent on social relations (Abubakar, 2021: 41).

The concept of civil society reached its importance after the industrial revolution. In the modern sense, civil society is “a community of individuals who are not under the control of the state, but rather make their decisions independently and engage in social activities (TDK, 2020). Bodin (1530-1596), Hobbes (1588-1679), Locke (1632-1704), Jacques Rousseau (1712-1778), Ferguson (1724-1816), Paine (1737-1809), Hegel (1770-1831), Tocqueville (1805-1850), Marx (1818-1883) and Gramsci (1891-1937) could be counted among the theorists who contributed to the development of the concept of civil society.

The concept of civil society, first used by Locke in 1690, remained on the agenda until Tocqueville's solutions to democracy. It gained importance again after a long silence until the 1970s, when it re-emerged in the democratization campaigns of Soviet-type political systems in Europe (Erdogan, 1998: 205).

It is clear that the new political searches that started after the collapse of the regimes in the Eastern Bloc played a significant role in the re-emergence of the discussions on civil society. Thus, the first task of the new democracies established by those who left the former Soviet Bloc was to re-establish the organizational structures that make up the civil society (Tamer, 2010). The term “NGO” has been common concept in public and business. The concept of NGO's can be referred as a group of intrinsically motivated people that preserve and enhance people's rights coordinately (Brodhead, 1987).

NGO's main aim is to enhance civil society through preserving rights; besides, they push society forward in terms of development and innovation (candid.org). Civil society refers to the intermediate level between the state and society. In today's world, elements of civil society play an important role in all areas of life such as social, political, economic and cultural.

2.2. Historical Development of Non-Governmental Organizations

As a result of the technological and economic developments in Europe since the 9th century, and the Pope's acceptance as a spiritual leader in the 11th Century, supervisory changes have occurred in the states and societies. In the 12th and 13th Centuries, organized social developments began to take place in Europe. Different lifestyles that emerged with the economic developments and enrichment in the 13th Century led to the development of civil society. The transition from the agricultural society to the industrial society transferred the power gathered in the family to the individuals. As a result of these developments, the "Guilds", which made arrangements for social life, formed the foundations of civil society. While economic developments enhanced trade, they also caused migration. While immigration weakened feudalism, it caused the development of the bourgeoisie and laid the foundations of capitalism. As a result of these developments, the state was surrounded by the church elites, the

state elites, the urban elites and the lower class (Proletariat) who had no property. While this situation revealed concepts such as equality, freedom and the rule of law, which are important factors of social life, it also laid the foundations of NGO's (Polat, 2020: 29).

NGOs was not as effective in Europe as in USA. NGO's in Europe are basically organized as British type or French type. The British type of civil society state understanding is based on the principle of reshaping according to the requirements of the age in the light of historical and social savings. The French type of civil society-state understanding, on the other hand, is based on the creation of the future with a fictional mind, ignoring historical and social accumulations (Polat, 2020: 31).

In 1807, Britain had gradually become conscious about slavery, which was forming the mentality of NGOs, who fought back against slavery, and started their first planned, powerful movement. For instance, when the International Committee of the Red Cross; The ICRC was established in Switzerland in 1856 and American Friends the Service Committee was established in 1917, NGOs focused on the wars and their impacts on people. From the first 20 years of late 20th century, NGOs attached importance to opposite thoughts to find ideal solutions. At that time, NGOs aimed to find the source of problems rather than remarking them (Potapkina, 2009: 8).

NGOs have always been in civil society throughout the history, but they were seen vital in society and increased supporters a considerable extend in last two decades of 20th Century (Lewis, 2009).

2.3. Functions and Structure of Non-Governmental Organizations

An Non Governmental Organization is public based organization that aims to preserve and enhance societies' rights without any financial worries (www.ngojobs.eu). The defining of an NGO is so, "private, self-governing, not-for-profit organization dedicated to alleviate human suffering; and/or providing education, health care, economic development, environmental protection, human rights, and conflict resolution; and/or encouraging the establishment of democratic institutions and civil society" (Aall, 2005: 89).

NGOs focus on issues of their own sites of establishment; which means, aims and necessities can be changeable based on their audience. Non-governmental organisations have been gradually securing their positions (Klugman, 2000: 98).

Known as "NGO", this civil movement has been referred several alternative names such as "non-profit", "voluntary" and "civil society" organizations. NGOs are coordinative community who withstand unfair treats regardless of their quantity (Lewis, 2009). NGOs are fully equipped, organized and balanced communities who are resolutely target driven, realise their goals; but if necessary, they are in coordination for their audience (Aall, 2005: 124).

Modern-day society consists of public sector, private sector and civil society (as the third sector). It is obvious that public and private sectors are not efficient enough to handle

insolvable communal problems. That's why it is a obligation to count in the third sector named NGO's- Pioneer of the progress and democracy in developed countries- in process while social issues encountered are solved with a bottom-up approach. NGOs are established with the aim of social purposes because they are far beyond the mentality of public and private sectors. NGO's, as the representers of civil society, aim to solve social problems to ensure progress and improvement in society (Polat, 2020).

NGO's are seen as a brand new sector right after public and private sectors because their main aim is to preserve and enhance every civil action. NGOs most known activity is to keep people up to date with the services they find it difficult to reach. The other one is to defend people's rights in case of unfair treats. These two activities are always coordinative. Besides, NGOs have other roles as well to promote social life, even environmentally and cultural issues (Lewis, 2009).

The work undertaken by NGOs is wide-ranging but NGO roles can be usefully analysed as having three main components: implementer, catalyst and partner (Lewis, 2009). The implementer's main focus is to deal with mobilization and hence the transportation of the resources to provide goods and facilities to those who are in need of them. Service delivery for the most fields like healthcare, microfinance, agricultural extension, emergency relief and human rights and such are carried out by NGOs. The aforementioned task, that is implementer role, has increased due to the NGOs increasingly contraction by the governments and donors with an accessibility to reformand privatisation policies to conduct and perform specific tasks in exchange for payment. On top of that, the particular role has become much more prominent as a result of the NGOs increasing response to the man-made, artificial emergencies or other natural occurrences like disasters with humanitarian assistance. One of the ways to define the catalyst role is, the ability to inspire, facilitate, contribute and thus improve the thinking and action to promote social transformation. The effort may be directed in several ways like towards the individual persons themselves or groups in communities in the area or among other developing actors or groups like government itself, business related persons or donors. The included persons, sides and groups might be the grassroots organizing, group formation, gender and empowerment work, lobbying and advocacy work and eventually the means for attempting to influence even wider policy processes by means of innovation and policy entrepreneurship (Lewis, 2009).

When it comes to structure, NGOs vary greatly. They vary in size as well as formality or informality. They might be large as well as small, just like they might be formal or informal and last but not the least bureauratic or flexible. Additionally, as for funding, most are externally-funded whereas the others depend on local resources for the matter (Lewis, 2009).

There are many types of NGOs. Associations, foundations, unions, chambers, stock exchanges and cooperatives are the most important ones. It is not correct to say that NGOs are under one roof. Because NGOs carry out their business under at least five components (Abubakar, 2021: 42)

NGOs use three basic strategic tools to serve successfully and efficiently. By using these three tools, the role of NGOs is both facilitated and empowered. The first tool of NGOs is framing. Framing is the value of NGOs and it is a tool used to increase power. Framing motivates collective action of strategic efforts. The second strategic tool of NGOs is the international coalition building method. The third strategy is scale shifting. Scale shifting, provides NGOs' tools to do work in a new way (Şaşmaz, 2012).

NGOs have some peculiarities of their own. These features include (Abubakar, 2021; Akyıldız, 2021: 28):

- Volunteering and voluntary membership,
- General membership rather than specific membership,
- Can be organized formally or informally,
- To serve voluntarily and efficiently, in an open and transparent framework must work,
- NGOs are non-profit,
- The source of their income is clear,
- Income-expenses are transparent required.
- Auditing.
- Do not have an internal hierarchy but have horizontal relationship,
- Contrary to political parties, a more radical, open, clear and courageous attitude towards problems they wear,
- In order for an entity to be defined as an NGO it exists as a private person independent of the state must be,

NGOs adhere to some basic principles during their work. These principles include (Abubakar, 2021): One of the most important principles is morality. The most basic foundations of NGOs to serve the society are the concepts of ethics and morality. NGOs provide service based on the framework of law, namely legitimacy. Other NGO principles are aesthetics, merit, sincerity and justice.

Since NGOs are one of the most important actors of globalization, they are among the important tools used very seriously by global powers. Although non-state organizations in every society date back to ancient times, the importance of NGOs has especially increased after the Second World War.

NGOs have many functions. These functions can be listed as (Güneş, 2004: 2; Akyıldız, 2021, 29);

- Helping individuals to express their demands by creating public opinion,
- By providing the formation of a pluralistic society structure, to be an element, a balancing act against the commodification and dominant market values in the market,
- With a participatory and pluralistic culture to train individuals who have gained management experience,
- By producing pilot projects and finding resources for these projects, to receive responsibilities in parallel or alternative to government policies in education, social welfare and employment,
- Acting as a kind of counterbalance to the impositions of the state and the market,
- States are actively involved for various reasons against global problems affecting the whole world by taking steps that it cannot take.

It is also very important to note that, NGOs of today's world have gradually yet rapidly become one of the most important parts of the international response to conflicts, disagreements and emergency health measures. These aspects of the matter are far beyond the traditional, usual aid goals of providing food, shelter, water and sanitation etc. for the ones who are in need (Lewis, 2009).

Working within the framework of private law, committed to the notion of the rule of law NGOs can work together with public and private forces by developing relations at the national and international level.

2.4. Change and Non-Governmental Organizations

Along with globalization, there are positive and negative developments that affect human and social life in the world. Among these developments, rapid population growth, limited resources, having limited resources and the distribution of these resources, and the international struggles for the use of resources can be counted. In addition, developments in the field of communication and technology have made it necessary to change and comply with it.

The most important issue for NGOs, which are established for many purposes such as benefiting the society, protecting the interests of their members, and providing various services to the society and its members, can be stated as the establishment of social efficiency and the fulfillment of missions (Yanay and Yanay, 2008: 66).

Structure is an important element of organizations. At the same time, structure has an impact on the effectiveness and efficiency of organizations. Change, on the other hand, is an irresistible reality of today that to have influence on everything. Changes in the organizational structures of non-governmental organizations and their reasons are an important issue that needs to be examined.

The ever-changing conditions of today's world bring opportunities and threats. Organizations that take the opportunities continue their existence by keeping up with the change. On the other hand, organizations that cannot adapt to change will face the danger of extinction over time. Adapting to change has become a more important issue for non-governmental organizations in terms of their mission of guiding and supporting the society.

Since the last decade of 20th Century, NGO's have been seen as a global movement that shaped from simple to complex. In other words, NGO's are constructed by local coalescence as well as global campaigns. There is a perpetual cooperation between these institutions.

The experienced changes make states, international actors and companies stronger. On the other hand, individuals and societies are affected more and more negatively by these developments. For this reason, the need for non-governmental organizations has been increasing day by day and this need will continue to increase in the future. In order to meet this need of individuals and society, these organizations must have an innovative, changer, proactive and flexible structure. At the same time, their ability to react quickly will be another important feature.

Three issues are important with which the concept of non-governmental organization is related. Those topics are globalisation, inequality and insecurity. Change can happen in NGO's roles, relations, capacities and reliabilities as the cooperation and helps to NGO reduce. It is vital that NGOs adapt to these changes. NGOs, as an actor in progressing global civil society, can help forming compensative power for the processes that exclude and exploit people through redelivering the currencies and chances, injecting social values to the market processes and holding the economic foundations responsible from their actions (Edwards, Hulme and Wallace, 1999).

21st Century's modern world has witnessed global challenges regarding the environment that are the main focuses of both deliberative and slightly unstable debates in varying fields such as politics, social and science. One of the most important alterations in the established and application of public policies is generally associated with the involvement of civil society in environmental governance (Betsil and Corell, 2008: 3).

2.5. Non-Governmental Organizations and Structural Change in the Future

The modern world is changing more rapidly every day, and the needs of people and societies have constantly been affected by these changes. Social changes affect NGOs and alter expectations from them. In a rapidly changing world, NGOs must at least adapt to change in order to realize their existence purposes. Among the recommendations of Willig (2019) on how NGOs can respond to changing world in the future, he says; “understand what your asset is, create space for out-of-the-box possibilities, look outside your organization and be relationship-oriented, governance matters and mindset is the solution”

One of the important problems experienced in NGOs is not being able to meet the demands of the external environment and not being able to keep up with the changes. Especially

in today's complex world, this is an important problem for non-governmental organizations. Non-governmental organizations try to eliminate situations that are not taken into account by the public and private sectors, but that create disadvantages for employees. In order to adapt to the changes, non-governmental organizations need to make structural, managerial and procedural changes. To progress and harden the frame of NGO's it is a must to follow innovative development and preserve present layouts (Pearce, 2000).

With the highly improved technologies, communication and processes' time are shortened, which means, NGO's reach problematic situations faster than ever; but without coordinative and well-organized pieces, these techno devices and their components would not be effecient enough to help NGO's achieve their goals (niilmuniversity.in).

According to Miles (1980, 8), organizations are responsible for their self regulations. Especially today's change has an impact on the basic elements of organizations such as task, structure, technology and employees. In accordance with this basic idea, non-governmental organizations should prefer a flexible and collaborative structure that can respond quickly to change in order to meet the expectations of their target audiences and maintain their existence.

Innovative ideas have been gradually highlighted in NGOs whereas in some local areas, conventional movements can still work to reach the aim. As problematic issues appear and get more complicated, world of work notice the need of organized, innovative and technology oriented social movements (Kent, Armstrong and Obrecht, 2013).

Although funding in the future of the total scale and growth of funding for international humanitarian action appear impressive, they, and more importantly, their impact, remain insufficient to meet the challenges of today, let alone tomorrow. The availability, conditions, and predictability of funding for humanitarian action are critical concern for any organisation without a doubt, but funding alone cannot create genuine capacity for action. With the increasing awareness in society and business life, NGOs will have enough pecuniary resources to make their objectives real, but it is a obligation to company the other promoters to achieve their goals (Kent, Armstrong and Obrecht, 2013).

3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

NGOs are one of the important actors of social life in terms of their aims. In today's world, as people get lonely, organizations get stronger. NGOs are an important force that can support individuals and control social functioning in the social structure where organizations are strengthened. All organizations, whether public or private, are affected by the changes, and NGOs cannot remain indifferent to these changes. NGOs that form a part of society are affected by changes in society and organizations. Because the target audiences of NGOs are also in this society and are affected by the change. NGOs, as the third sector, have to deal with many positive and negative issues due to their positions. These issues should be evaluated on the basis of target audiences and a strategy should be produced accordingly. This situation is the characteristics of NGOs that distinguishes them from other organizations.

NGOs can survive in parallel with their ability to meet the expectations of their target audiences. Thanks to these characteristics, they should have the ability to think differently and act faster than other organizations. These abilities help them achieve the desired results along with an effective organizational structure, sincere employees and an effective communication strategy. Although organizational structures are flexible and flat, they should support team-based work and quick decision making and risk taking.

The changing political, social, economic and legal conditions should be evaluated by NGOs, and they should be able to determine proactive action styles on the expectations of the public and private sector and the expectations of their target audiences, or at least reconcile these expectations. The current Covid-19 Pandemic has necessitated the re-examination of many systems on a social basis. In this process, communication and information technologies have come to the fore and organizations using these technologies have been able to continue their activities. NGOs have important duties in solving the economic, social and societal problems experienced during the pandemic period and in developing strategies for these problems. Considering that similar situations that will occur in the future, NGOs will be able to carry out their duties in more challenging conditions, and besides a structure that can think and act quickly, flexible, solution-oriented and proactive, leaders with a future vision and the expectations of their target audiences can be more effectively coordinated with the public and private sectors that they can afford.

What the possible researches in the future will focus on is a variable. However, it should be noted that, those that might focus on different aspects and sides of sustainability in the civil society sector and on areas respectively environmental dynamism, environmental competitiveness, transparency and strategy in the context of both civil society and non-governmental organizations (Metin, 2017: 198).

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